

REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF JOURNALISM IN OUR COUNTRY
AND THE HISTORY OF THE FIELD OF JOURNALISM

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Abstract: This article provides information about the reforms implemented in the field of journalism in our country and the history of the field of journalism.

Key words: journalism, mass media, the press, technology, internet, mass communication, articles, information security.

The first shoots of journalism in works on the history of journalism made of clay in China in BC and later Plasterboards in Rome, and carved on ceramics in Japan It is shown that they are special maiumotnoms cooked in the khumdon. This publications did not become popular by themselves, because their number increased and distribution is extremely difficult. Later, with the invention of paper such publications began to be replaced by qaiyazm a leaflets.

Differences in the emergence and formation of Uzbek journalism a leaflets have taken over m aium o 'nn. For example, still Uzbek its function at a time when journalism was not formed in the fundamental sense Mukimi, the great representatives of Uzbek democratic literature, Furqat, Zavqi and others exposed the social evils of their time those who spread their humorous poems in the form of qayyozm a, are seen by many people those who hung and glued to places.

Handwritten leaflets with community development (rule writing and due to the difficulty of reproduction) does not meet the demand. Science - the growth of technology and the literal invention of the printing press is crucial in creating the press.

According to the President's decision of June 27, 2022 "On measures to support the mass media and develop the field of journalism", from July 1, 2022 to July 1, 2025, the mass media profit tax will be reduced to 50 it was introduced to pay interest at reduced tax rates.

In order to regularly encourage active journalists, the authors of up to 100 best materials published in the mass media will be awarded with a cash prize of up to 50 times the amount of the base calculation.

The press lives with the spirit of the processes and comprehensive reforms taking place in the society. The important changes taking place in the country and the shortcomings are reflected in the mass media. In this sense, it is necessary to recognize that the influence and effectiveness of the word of the press in our country has changed significantly in recent years. The legal basis of freedom of speech, topic and opinion was created. Newspapers and magazines are taking a bold step towards the atmosphere of openness and transparency, which they have dreamed of for many years. The increasing number of in-depth analytical articles in our press, including the results of journalist inquiries, can be a proof of our opinion.

Today, Internet journalism, which is developing further and acquiring new directions, is distinguished by its comprehensiveness and the fact that its audience knows no boundaries. Internet journalism, which is considered a type of modern mass media, the development of mass media, expansion of its tasks, sharp changes in the field of production and technology, and the complexity of relations between journalism and society, put new tasks before journalists. Nowadays, it is important to train universal journalists who can simultaneously write news, acquire the skills of interviewing, taking photos and videos, and prepare materials for the Internet. Today, mass media plays a major role in society. In addition, the role of mass media in the socio-political life of Uzbekistan is rapidly strengthening. If we look at the history of mass media activity in our country, in 1991 only 395 media outlets were operating in our country. By 2016, their number reached 1,437, and today their number is close to 2,000, and most of them are private. Modern specialists for mass media in Uzbekistan.

In order to improve the training system, the University of Journalism and Mass Communications was established. Organizations such as Creative Union of Journalists of Uzbekistan, National Press Center, National Association of Electronic Mass Media, Public Fund for Support and Development of Independent Print Mass Media and News Agencies and International Press Club are successfully operating.

Representatives of leading foreign mass media, including Reuters, France Press, BBC, The Economist, Xinhua, "Voice of America", "Fergana.Ru", Eurasianet reporters work freely in Uzbekistan.

Actually, in a democratic legal state and a fair civil society, the reputation of journalists will be much higher. Because they are the real fourth power, one of the unique spiritual and educational bridges between the state and the people.

Consequently, a journalist feels responsible for every word, is responsible and accountable to the people and society.

In this regard, journalists are required to adapt to the requirements of the times and improve their work efficiency. This will undoubtedly serve to ensure the information security of our country.

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